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(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The plants traded at the nursery of Jatikarya, Bekasi District, West Java Province, Indonesia

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Abstract

Nursery is a places to buy, sell, care, and maintain various types of beneficial plants. The type and value of selling plants varies between regions depending on the needs and supply. This study aims to determine the species and economic value of plants traded in the nursery of Jatikarya, Bekasi District, West Java Province, Indonesia. Thereseearch was conducted a survey and interviews to the nursery owners or employees. The list of questionnaire were local name of the plants, source of acquisition, supplying, purchasing and selling price of each plants. A number of 130 species belonging 96 genera and 56 families traded at the Jatikarya nursery and the selling price was about 5,000 – 5.000,000 IDR. The trading plants uses as ornament, sources of fruit, ground cover, and shade. The selling value of each species depends on the size, supply, age, method of breeding, and maintenance. The bonsai plants such as Korean banyan (*Ficus campanulata*/ Moraceae) and *anting putri* (*Wrightia religiosa*/ Apocynaceae) have expensive. The rambutans (*Nephelium lappaceum*) and guavas (*Psidium guajava*) are the most popular of fruit plants. The *krokots* (*Portulaca glandiflora*) and lili paris (*Chlorophytum comosum*) are easy to propagate with affordable prices (5,000-10,000 IDR) per unit. In order to increase the productivity of nursery and conservation, it is important to promote and to socialize the role of plants.

Keywords: Nursery; Jatikarya; *Ficus campanulata*

1. Introduction

Indonesia has a diversity of around 30,000 plant species. The distribution of biodiversity between in the region, island and country is varied. Based on the biogeography of plants, indonesia is divided into three zones, namely is western Malesiana, central Malesiana and eastern Malesiana [1]. The Dipterocarpaceae such as meranti (*Shorea spp.*) are found in western Malesiana, pandan (*Pandanus spp*) and matoa (Sapindaceae) are found in the eastern Malesiana.

The use of plants by human results trading plants by local communities [2]. The transaction of buying and selling plants can be found in the traditional markets, modern markets and nursery. Silalahi et al [3] stated that the buying and selling of medicinal plants in the Kabanjahe traditional market had been carried out for decades and found more than 240 species of medicinal plants to be traded. Various benefits from buying and selling have grown, among others, as a source of income, exchange of local knowledge and preserving local wisdom [4].

In the “traditional markets and supermarkets are used by local communities to buy and to sell plants for some purposes such as fruits, vegetable, staple food [5], while in the nursery are also carried out nurseryes and maintenance of plants that are traded [6-7]. Its shows that in the nursery have thev very complex of problem, so its need the plant management which resulted the sustainable the nursery [8].

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Various types of plants are traded in nursery such as ornamental plants, fruit-producing plants, and shade plants [8]. Plants that are traded in nursery are thought to differ from one location to another. Some factors that are thought to influence include capital [9], plant habitus [10], and nursery size [7]. Singh et al [10] stated that plant species with tree seeds in nursery in urban areas were less than those in peri urban nursery.

Since the 2000s, in Jakarta area including Bekasi begun nursery to answer the needs of plants by residents of Jakarta and its surroundings. Silalahi and Sihotang [11] stated that trading plants in nursery in Bekasi are dominated by herbal plants because they had smaller size and faster propagation. The people in the city have a narrow land, so they rarely use trees as garden plants.

Jatikarya is of the regional of the Bekasi district that has prospects for buying and selling various types of plants. Until now, the research of nursery trading plant is still limited, even though the prospects for nurseries in the economic and ecological fields need to be studied as an effort to preserve biodiversity and as a source of income. This study aims to determine the trade and diversity of nursery plants in Jatikarya, Bekasi District. The results of this study are expected to become one of the plants database.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Data collection in the field

To find out the nursery types at Jatikarya, surveys and observations were conducted. The data Plants were photos, local names, habitus and sale value. To complete the data, the identity of the selection or employee in the nursery is also asked, including name, age, gender and ethnicity. Identification was done by comparing the types of plants obtained with the Flora of Java Volume II-III book [12-13].

2.2. Analysis of data

Data analysis is carried out qualitatively including the types of plants being traded, habitus and selling prices. Analysis of plant diversity carried out descriptively by grouping plants based on habitus (trees, shrubs, herbs), benefits (ornamental plants, shade, and other functions), genus and family.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Description of traders in nursery of Jatikarya

The traders nurseries of Jatikarya are Javanese, Sundanese and Betawi ethnic that has been trading for 8-31 yeas 8-31 years. All traders are male, aged 38-50 years old. Every nursery has employees whose job is to preserve plants while helping buy-sell transactions. Buying Plant and selling transactions at Jatikarya Nursery starts from 08.00-17.00.

Figure 1 Structuring of plants at the nursery of Jatikarya, Bekasi District, West Java Province, Indonesia. A. Display the front by arranging a simple landscape; B. Display by arranging plants by hanging plants on the nursery ceiling

The number of employees' 1-3 people depends on the size and amount of work. To attract customers, the owners or employees organize the front display of the nursery attractively by using its own plants while at the same time making efficient use of space and land (Figure 1a). Placement of plants in nursery space is adjusted to the needs of the sun, size, and the need for water. Small plants that require high humidity are hung on the nursery ceiling and protected from direct light using paranet (Figure 1b).

The nursery also provide various other materials such as pots, planting media, seeds, fertilizers and other plant maintenance tools (roasting, spray, ornamental stones) to customers (Figure 2). When viewed from the volume, the sales of planting media and pots are most in demand and the size and type of pots are adjusted to the type of plants to be cultivated. Potted plants with a diameter of 50-100 cm are used for fruit trees, while pots with a diameter of 10-30 cm are used for ornamental plants.

Figure 2 The planting media (organic fertilizer) and pots are traded at the nursery of Jatikarya, Bekasi District, West Java Province, Indonesia

In addition to buying and selling transactions at the nursery, weeding, fertilizing, and other treatments are also carried out. Sihotang et al [7] (2019) stated that for efficiency in nursery management good management is needed so that the continuity and development of the nursery can be improved. In nurseries some traders also use plastic waste from mineral water, which can directly reduce waste (Figure 3). Some plants are propagation with cuttings such as wijaya kusuma, cactus and *Draecaena*. *Aglaonema* spp. bred by separating some buds that have been formed. The nurseries carried out by nursery owners are mostly in the form of stem cuttings and by the separation of the parent plant clumps. It aims to minimize production costs so that the selling price can be reduced.

Figure 3 The activities at the nursery of Jatikarya, Bekasi District, West Java Province, Indonesia. A. Nurseries by separating clumps and stem cuttings. B. Waste plastic used mineral water as a nursery container.

3.2. Diversity of Plants

The research found 130 species belonging to 96 genera and 56 families (Figure 4). Most of the plants belonging to the Araceae, Arcaceae, and Asparagaceae families (Table 1). The Araceae plants are the ornamental plants that have attractive leaf characters such as *Aglaonema* spp and *Anthurium* spp. The *Aglaonema* spp are the plants that have colorful leaves with a relatively expensive selling price (200,000 IDR) and many devotees.

Figure 4 The number of families, genera and species are traded at the nursery of Jatikarya, Bekasi District, West Java Province, Indonesia.

Table 1 Local names, scientific names and benefits of plants at the nursery of Jatikarya, District, West Java Province, Indonesia

Family	Scientific name	Local name	Uses
Adiantaceae	<i>Adiantum</i> sp.1	<i>Suplir dolar</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Adiantum</i> sp.2	<i>Suplir keriting</i>	Ornamental plant
Agavaceae	<i>Agave variegata</i>	<i>Agave variegata</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Agave</i> sp	<i>Agave</i>	Ornamental plant
Amaranthaceae	<i>Alternanthera reineckii</i>	<i>Erpa</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Celosia cistata</i>	<i>Jengger ayam</i>	Ornamental plant
Amaryllidaceae	<i>Crynum asiaticum</i>	<i>Bakung</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Zephyranthes candida</i>	<i>Bunga bawang</i>	Ornamental plant
Anonaceae	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i>	<i>Globokan tiang</i>	Shading
Apocynaceae	<i>Alstonia shcolaris</i>	<i>Pulai</i>	Shading
	<i>Pulmeria rubra</i>	<i>Kamboja bali</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Adenium</i> sp.	<i>Kamboja jepang</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Wrightia religiosa</i>	<i>Anting putri</i>	Ornamental plant
Araceae	<i>Aglaonema crispum</i>	<i>Sri rejeki</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Aglaonema picta</i>	<i>Beras tumpah</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Aglaonema</i> sp.1	<i>Snow white</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Aglaonema</i> sp.2	<i>Aglonema</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Aglaonema</i> sp.3	<i>Aglonema lipstick</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Anthurium crystallinum</i>	<i>Kuping gajah</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Anthurium</i> sp.1	<i>Gelombang cinta</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Anthurium</i> sp.2	<i>Anturium</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Anthurium</i> sp.3	<i>Anturium kol</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Epipremnum aureum</i>	<i>Sirih gading</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Epipremnum aureum</i>	<i>Sirih gading variegata</i>	Ornamental plant

	<i>variegata</i>		
	<i>Spathiphyllum</i> sp.	<i>Spatufilium</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Zamioculcas zamiifolia</i>	<i>Daun dolar</i>	Ornamental plant
Araliaceae	<i>Schefflera aboricola</i>	<i>Wali songo</i>	Ornamental plant
Arecaceae	<i>Crisalidocarpus lutescens</i>	<i>Palem Kuning</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Cyrtostachys renda</i>	<i>Palem merah</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Dypsis lutescens</i>	<i>Palem Putri</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Hyophorbe lagenicaulis</i>	<i>Palem Botol</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Livistona saribus</i>	<i>Palem kipas</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Phoenix roebelenii</i>	<i>Palem ponix</i>	Ornamental plant
Asparagaceae	<i>Asparagus densiflorus</i>	<i>Ekor tupai</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Chlorophytum comosum</i>	<i>Lili Paris</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Cordilyne terminalis</i>	<i>Hanjuan Merah</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Dracaena marginata</i> var <i>tricolor</i>	<i>Trikolor</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Sansiviera trivasciata</i>	<i>Lidah mertua</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Sansiviera</i> sp.	<i>Lidah mertua variegata</i>	Ornamental plant
Aspleniaceae	<i>Asplenium scolopendrium</i>	<i>Kadaka</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Asplenium nidus</i>	<i>Paku sarang burung</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Asplenium</i> sp.1	<i>Kadaka gelombang cinta</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Asplenium</i> sp.2	<i>Kadaka Keriting</i>	Ornamental plant
Athyriaceae	<i>Diplazium</i> sp.	<i>pakis paku</i>	Ornamental plant
Begoniaceae	<i>Begonia</i> sp.1	<i>Begonia</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Begonia</i> sp.2	<i>Begonia coklat</i>	Ornamental plant
Bombacaceae	<i>Durio zibethinus</i>	<i>Durian</i>	Fruit resources
Boraginaceae	<i>Nemophila menziesii</i>	<i>Blue eyes</i>	Ornamental plant
Bromeliaceae	<i>Bromelia</i> sp.1	<i>Bromelia hijau</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Bromelia</i> sp.2	<i>Bromelia lipstick</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Bromelia</i> sp.3	<i>Bromelia coklat</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Bromelia</i> sp.4	<i>Giant</i>	Ornamental plant
Cactaceae	<i>Epiphyllum oxipetalum</i>	<i>Wijaya kusuma</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Opuntia cochenillifera</i>	<i>Centong</i>	Ornamental plant
Cannaceae	<i>Canna discolor</i>	<i>Ganyong</i>	Ornamental plant
Casuarinaceae	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>	<i>Cemara udang</i>	Ornamental plant
Combretaceae	<i>Combretum indicum</i>	<i>Melati belanda</i>	Shading
	<i>Terminalia mantaly</i>	<i>Ketapang kaca</i>	Shading
Commelinaceae	<i>Rhoeo discolor</i>	<i>Adam Hawa</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Zebrina pendula</i>	<i>Sabrina</i>	Ornamental plant

Crassulaceae	<i>Kalanchoe</i> sp.	<i>Cocor bebek</i>	Ornamental plant
Cupressaceae	<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i>	<i>Cemara lilin</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Cupressus papuanus</i>	<i>Cemara Papua</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Juniperus comunnis</i>	<i>Cemara Salju</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Thuja occidentales</i>	<i>Cemara kipas</i>	Ornamental plant
Cycadaceae	<i>Cycas revulota</i>	<i>Sikas</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Cycas</i> sp.	<i>Pakis haji</i>	Ornamental plant
Echinoceae	<i>Echinodorus palifolius</i>	<i>Melati Air</i>	Ornamental plant
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha siamensis</i>	<i>Teh-tehan</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Ecoecaria cochinchinensis</i>	<i>Sampang darah</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i>	<i>Kestuba</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i>	<i>Puring Kirana</i>	Ornamental plant
Equisetaceae	<i>Equisetum debile</i>	<i>Bambu Air</i>	Ornamental plant
Fabaceae	<i>Arachis pintoii</i>	<i>Kacang-kacangan</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Bahunia purpurea</i>	<i>Butterfly</i>	Ornamental plant
Heloconiaceae	<i>Heliconia paittacorom</i>	<i>Sepit udang</i>	Ornamental plant
Hemerocallidaceae	<i>Dianella tasmanica</i>	<i>Lili brasil</i>	Ornamental plant
Hydrangeaceae	<i>Hydrangea macrophylla</i>	<i>Brokoli hias</i>	Ornamental plant
Iridaceae	<i>Neomarica longifolia</i>	<i>Iris</i>	Ornamental plant
Lamiaceae	<i>Coleus blumei</i>	<i>Miana</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Mentha × piperita</i>	<i>Daun mint</i>	Medicinal plant, vegetable
Liliaceae	<i>Lilium</i> sp.	<i>Lili umbi</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Ophiopogon japonicus</i>	<i>Ucai</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Sansiviera</i> sp.	<i>Lidah mertua</i>	Ornamental plant
Lythraceae	<i>Cuphea hyssopifolia</i>	<i>Taiwan</i>	Ornamental plant
Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus tiliaceus</i>	<i>Waru variegata</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Hibiscus rosa sinensis</i>	<i>Spatu merah</i>	Ornamental plant
Marantaceae	<i>Maranta arundinacea</i>	<i>Maranta</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Calathea lutea</i>	<i>Talatea</i>	Ornamental plant
Moraceae	<i>Ficus campanulata</i>	<i>Beringin Korea</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Ficus</i> sp.1	<i>Beringin sianto</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Ficus</i> sp.2	<i>Beringin variegata</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Streblus asper</i>	<i>Serut</i>	Ornamental plant
Myrtaceae	<i>Myrciaria cauliflora</i>	<i>Anggur Brazil</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	<i>Jambu biji</i>	Fruit resources
	<i>Syzygium oleana</i>	<i>Pucuk Merah</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Syzygium jambos</i>	<i>Jambu mawar</i>	Fruit resources
	<i>Syzygium malaccense</i>	<i>Jambu Jamaika</i>	Fruit resources

Nelumbonaceae	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	<i>Lotus pink</i>	Ornamental plant
Nyctagynaceae	<i>Bougenvillea spectabilis</i>	<i>Bougenvillea bonsai</i>	Ornamental plant
Nymphaceae	<i>Nymphaea</i> sp.	<i>Teratai</i>	Ornamental plant
Oleaceae	<i>Jasminum</i> sp.	<i>Jasmin</i>	Ornamental plant
Poaceae	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>	<i>Bambu kuning</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Thyrsostachys siamensis</i>	<i>Bambu jepang</i>	Ornamental plant
Piperaceae	<i>Piper betle</i>	<i>Sirih hijau</i>	Medicinal plant
	<i>Piper crocratum</i>	<i>Sirih merah</i>	Ornamental plant
Polypodiaceae	<i>Plathycerium bifurcatum</i>	<i>Paku tanduk rusa</i>	Ornamental plant
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca glandiflora</i>	<i>Krokot</i>	Ornamental plant
Rosaceae	<i>Rosa hybrida</i>	<i>Mawar pink</i>	Ornamental plant
Rubiaceae	<i>Ixora siaminensis</i>	<i>Asoka pink</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Ixora</i> sp.1	<i>Asoka kuning</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Ixora</i> sp.2	<i>Asoka putih</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Mussaenda philipca</i>	<i>Nusa indah</i>	Ornamental plant
Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum frustecens</i>	<i>Cabe rawit Thailand</i>	Spices
	<i>Capsicum annum</i>	<i>Cabe kecil</i>	Spices
	<i>Solanum melogena</i>	<i>Terong</i>	Vegetable
Rutaceae	<i>Citrus amblycarpa</i>	<i>Jeruk limau</i>	Spices
	<i>Citrus aurantiafolium</i>	<i>Jeruk nipis</i>	Spices, medicinal plant
	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	<i>Jeruk manis</i>	Fruit resources
	<i>Citrus</i> sp	<i>Jeruk peras</i>	Fruit resources
	<i>Evodia suaveolens</i>	<i>Jodiak</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Murraya paniculata</i>	<i>Kemuning</i>	Ornamental plant, medicinal plant
Sapindaceae	<i>Dimocarpus longan</i>	<i>Klengkeng</i>	Fruit resources
	<i>Nephelium lappaceum</i>	<i>Rambutan</i>	Fruit resources
Urticaceae	<i>Pilea cadieri</i>	<i>Mutiara</i>	Ornamental plant
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	<i>Anggur hijau</i>	Fruit resources
Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i>	<i>Lantana orange</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Lantana montevidensis</i>	<i>Lantana pink</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Lantana</i> sp.1	<i>Lantana kuning</i>	Ornamental plant
	<i>Lantan</i> sp.2	<i>Lantana putih</i>	Ornamental plant
Zingiberaceae	<i>Costus spicatus</i>	<i>Pacing</i>	Ornamental plant

Based on the life form, the traded plants at the Jatikarya nursery are herbs, shrubs and trees. Herb is the plant which have the plant stems contain a lot of water and its size relatively smaller compared to other types. These types are a choice for consumers with small yard or home garden. Most of the traded herbs have attractive leaves (*Aglonema* spp., *Bromelia* spp., and *Sansiviera* spp.).

Figure 5 The types of habitus plant at the nurseries of Jatikaya, Bekasi District, Java West Province, Indonesia. A. Herb (*Bromelia* sp.); B. Shurb (*Schefflera aboricola*); C. Shurb (*Bougenvillea spectabilis*); D. Tree (*Hibiscus tiliaceus*).

Bonsai plants which the rootstock is different from the upper stem were traded plants at the nurseries. The rootstock is large and sturdy, while the upper stem is a species with a dense branching pattern. To increase the number and size of clumps can be done by pruning (figure 5). The selling value of bonsai plants depends on the size and beauty of the structure of canopy.

Figure 6 The types of bonsai plants are traded at the nursery of Jatikarya, Bekasi District, Java West Province, Indonesia. A. Bonsai of Korean banyan (*Ficus campanulata*); B. Bonsai of *anting putri* (*Wrightia religiosa*)

The selling price of the traded plants varies between Rp. 5,000 to millions of rupiah. Several factors that influence the selling price include size, age, availability, maintenance and its trend value. In general, plants are directly proportional to size, therefore plants with large size are higher than others.

Some of the plants have higher consumers such as rambutans (*Nephelium lappaceum*) and guavas (*Psidium guajava*) and mangos (*Mangifera indica*). These are common plants that easily can be found in yard and gardens because of the fruit times. The ornamental plants which high demand are plants that easy to care (*Codiaeum variegatum*, *Equisetum debile*), and attractive leaves (*Aglaonema* spp, *Phylodendron* spp).

4. Conclusion

The research founded more than 130 species of plants traded in the Jatikarya nursery have selling price from 5,000 – 5,000,000 IDR. The price of each type of plant depends to size, supply, age, method of breeding, and maintenance. Bonsai plants such as Korean banyan (*Ficus campanulata*/ Moraceae) and *anting putri* (*Wrightia religiosa*/ Apocynaceae) are expensive. Rambutans (*Nephelium lappaceum*) and guavas (*Psidium guajava*) are the type of fruit trees that have a great demand.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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